

FEATURES OF IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION LEADERS

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Abstract: The article examines the problems of improving the professional competence of the heads of preschool education organizations, and the experience of working on the formation of the professional competence of young heads through the implementation of the methodical support model is presented. The stages of formation of professional competence are disclosed.

Key words: quality of education, professional qualification, leader, methodical support model, professional development.

Introduction:

Currently, the main task of the educational process is to produce a competitive specialist for the society. According to the results of the research, most employers prefer to sign a contract with an employee who has the skills of independent study, quick and effective decision-making when necessary, and constant analysis (reflection) of his work they see a slave. That is why the leader must first of all be educated, know the great life he lives, understand the laws of nature and society, be socially active, master the pedagogy of general and preschool education, children's psychology and physiology, and know the young characteristics of children. Also, the leader's approach to the analysis of events from a scientific point of view makes it possible to realize the success of the comprehensive development of the child. For this, the tasks of equipping the growing young generation with knowledge, restoring our spirituality, introducing them to world culture, masterpieces of our national culture, and raising them to be physically healthy and spiritually mature have been set. For this, the ability of each leader to demand and control himself is a guarantee of the fulfillment of the requirements set by our state for preschool education organizations.

The leader should have a high level of pedagogical skills, such as communication skills, thoroughly master the laws of pedagogical technique, speech, face, hand, leg and body movements, mime, gesture, pantomime). The leader should be able to observe the children, correctly analyze the reasons for their behavior and behavior, and use the means to influence them.

In order to make the young generation aware of the necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities, the leader should have the culture of speech and his speech should be able to reflect the following features.

- Clarity of speech.
- Willfulness of speech.
- Purity of speech.

Purity of speech (free from its various dialect words), expression only in literary language, jargon (words specific to professionals in a certain profession or field), barbarism

(addition of foreign words to the speech expressed in the language of a certain nation inappropriate use), free of vulgarism (words used in actions, swearing) and consoialism (speaking in formal speech in inappropriate situations) and the speech of the pedagogue is simple, should be fluent and understandable.

Literature review:

The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological research. Therefore, competence is "how the specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, plans for movement in consistently developing and complex processes means "ownership".

Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level.

Social competence - the ability to show activity in social relations, the ability to communicate with subjects in professional activities.

Special competence - preparation for organizing professional-pedagogical activity, rational solution of professional-pedagogical tasks, realistic assessment of activity results, consistent development of BKM, psychological, methodical, informational, creative, innovative and communicative competence on the basis of this competence. is thrown into z. They contain the following content:

Psychological competence - healthy psychological in the pedagogical process.

The ability to create an environment, to organize positive communication with students and other participants of the educational process, to be able to understand and eliminate various negative psychological conflicts in time, methodical competence - methodically rational organization of the pedagogical process, to complete the forms of educational or educational activities to be able to correctly determine, to choose methods and tools according to the purpose, to be able to use methods effectively, to use tools successfully; informational competence - searching for, collecting, sorting, processing necessary, important, necessary, useful information in the information environment and using it purposefully, appropriately, effectively; creative competence - a critical, creative approach to pedagogical activity, ability to demonstrate one's own creative skills, innovative competence - improving the pedagogical process, improving the quality of education, putting forward new ideas to increase the effectiveness of the educational process, and effectively implementing them into practice.

Communicative competence is the ability to communicate sincerely with all participants of the educational process, including students, to be able to listen to them, to have a positive influence on them.

Personal competence - to consistently achieve professional growth, to increase the level of competence, to demonstrate one's internal capabilities in professional activity.

Technological competence - mastering advanced technologies that enrich professional and pedagogical BKM, being able to use modern tools, techniques and technologies.

Extreme competence is the ability to make rational decisions and act correctly in emergency situations (natural disasters, technological process failure), when pedagogical conflicts arise.

Research methodology:

It is important to work on yourself and develop yourself in order to acquire professional and pedagogical competence. Self-development tasks are determined through self-analysis and self-assessment.

The formation of professional competence of the head of preschool educational organizations is a combination of professional and general human relations, as a result of which it will be possible not only to effectively manage the educational process, but also to successfully solve the difficulties that arise during the performance of tasks. This undoubtedly affects the improvement of professional pedagogical competence and the development of pedagogical skills. At this stage of educational development, the competency-based approach is the leading direction in the activities of preschool leaders. The professional competence of the heads of this preschool educational organization is the acquisition of experience, knowledge, skills, techniques and methods necessary for the precise performance of the competence tasks of the heads of the preschool educational organization.

Results:

The professional competence of the head of a preschool educational organization is a set of competencies: methodological, psychological and pedagogical, communicative, research, presentation, ICT competence, emotional competence.

Summary:

Practice shows that both of the above directions of professional training have their own problems. On the one hand, there is a lack of practical skills of students and graduates in organizing measures and procedures of pedagogical interaction. In particular, it is very difficult for the head of a preschool educational organization to attract children to the world of new things and events, to involve them in interesting activities, to turn them into a subject of activity. This is largely due to the fact that the professional training of future preschool education organization leaders is focused primarily on planning educational activities, implementing programs, mastering technologies, and organizing children's activities according to the intended process.

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